

PERSONALIZED ALGORITHMS FOR PREDICTING AND PREVENTING ADHESION RECURRENCE IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION

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Abstract. *The article presents the theoretical foundations, clinical observations, and experimental data supporting the development and effectiveness of a multifactorial model for predicting adhesion recurrence in patients with acute intestinal obstruction. A risk stratification algorithm based on the assessment of biochemical and morphometric markers (oxyproline, matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) extracellular matrix (ECM), fibroblast mitotic activity (FMA)) is described, along with an evaluation of the medical, social, and economic effectiveness of the proposed approach.*

Keywords: *acute intestinal obstruction, adhesions, prediction, prevention.*

Introduction

Adhesive disease of the abdominal cavity and its complication—acute adhesive intestinal obstruction (AAIO)—remain among the most relevant and challenging problems in abdominal surgery. According to international statistics, up to 75% of cases of mechanical intestinal obstruction are caused by adhesions, and repeat surgical interventions associated with this complication are among the most costly procedures in global clinical practice [2].

Despite the use of modern anti-adhesion agents and improvements in surgical techniques, the recurrence rate of adhesive intestinal obstruction remains significant, reaching 30–50% according to various sources. Traditional measures for preventing adhesion formation often overlook individual patient-specific pathogenic factors, including fibroblast metabolic activity, oxyproline synthesis levels, matrix metalloproteinase activity, as well as the acetylation phenotype, which directly influences susceptibility to fibrosis [3,4].

An additional complicating factor is that recurrences of adhesive intestinal obstruction often do not develop immediately but appear after a prolonged period—frequently several months or even years following the primary surgery. This significantly complicates both timely diagnosis and the implementation of effective preventive measures. Clinical manifestations are often nonspecific or subtle until the development of complete intestinal obstruction, which requires emergency surgical intervention. Repeat operations performed in the context of pronounced adhesion formation are associated with numerous challenges: markedly increased operative time, a higher risk of intraoperative organ injury, and an elevated likelihood of both intraoperative and postoperative complications [6].

Furthermore, to date, there are no universal and reliable indicators that allow early prediction of adhesion recurrence. Traditional clinical scales have low specificity and do not enable adequate stratification of patients according to risk level. At the same time, the use of biochemical markers—such as oxyproline, MMP-9, components of the extracellular matrix (ECM), and mediators of the immune-inflammatory response (fibroblast mitotic activity, FMA)—

opens up prospects for the development of individualized strategies that allow prediction of disease progression already in the early stages of the postoperative period [4].

The question of the justification for routine use of anti-adhesion barriers in all patients remains unresolved. Considering the limited resources of healthcare systems, a selective approach is necessary, whereby preventive measures are implemented primarily in patients with a reliably established high risk of adhesion formation. This requires the integration of simple, reliable, and accessible verification algorithms into practical surgical practice [5,6].

Existing methods, in most cases, do not allow for a comprehensive assessment of either changes in connective tissue metabolism or the combined impact of concomitant somatic diseases, the nature of previous surgical interventions, and the duration of hospitalization. Therefore, there is a need to develop a comprehensive prognostic algorithm that integrates clinical and historical data with biochemical and morphological characteristics [1,C.15-17; 2,C.276-283].

Research Objective: The objective of the study is to improve the effectiveness of treatment for patients with acute adhesive intestinal obstruction by enhancing methods for predicting and preventing recurrent adhesion formation.

Materials and Methods. This article is based on the results of a clinical and experimental study focused on the development, implementation, and evaluation of the effectiveness of a comprehensive model for predicting and preventing adhesion formation in patients with acute intestinal obstruction. The study included parallel clinical and experimental observations, which ensured a high level of evidence and substantiation for the proposed solutions.

The clinical and experimental study included 218 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of acute adhesive intestinal obstruction, who were treated between 2014 and 2023 at the Emergency Surgery Clinic of the Republican Scientific Center of Emergency Medical Care (RSC EMC) and its Khorezm branch, under the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. All patients were divided into two groups.:

Control group (n = 108): treatment was carried out according to standard protocols in accordance with accepted clinical guidelines. Control group (n = 108): treatment was carried out according to standard protocols in accordance with accepted clinical guidelines;

Main group (n = 110): in addition to conventional therapy, the patients received the predictive and preventive protocols developed by our team, which included individualized risk assessment using laboratory biomarkers and consideration of the acetylation phenotype.

The study included patients over 18 years of age, who were not pregnant, had a confirmed adhesive nature of intestinal obstruction, and had no concomitant oncological diseases (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Age distribution of patients

The figure illustrates the distribution of patients with acute adhesive intestinal obstruction across age categories in the control and main groups, as well as in the overall sample. The smallest number of patients was observed in the under-20 age group (8.7% of the total sample), while the largest proportion of patients fell within the 45–50 age range (21.1%). A similar trend was seen in both the control and main groups, indicating a balanced age distribution among the participants. The middle age categories (31–44 and 51–59 years) accounted for roughly equal proportions—about 14–17% of the total number of patients. In the older age subgroups (60–74 and ≥75 years), more than a quarter of all patients (28%) were represented, highlighting the significance of the problem in the elderly. Acute adhesive intestinal obstruction was most commonly observed in middle-aged and older patients, with a peak incidence between 45 and 50 years.

The mean age of the patients was 52.6 ± 12.4 years. Women predominated, accounting for 62.8% of the cohort (Table 1). More than 70% of the examined patients had a history of two or more abdominal surgeries. The proportion of patients with chronic comorbidities (cardiovascular, endocrine, and respiratory diseases) exceeded 50%. Analysis of hospitalization timing showed that approximately 45% of patients were admitted within the first 24 hours of symptom onset, whereas 18.8% sought medical care 72 hours or more after the onset of clinical manifestations.

Table 1

Distribution of patients by gender

Gender	Patient Groups				Total	
	Control group		Main group			
	n=108	%	n=110	%	n=218	%
Female	66	61.1	71	64.5	137	62.8
Male	42	38.9	39	35.5	81	37.2

Patients underwent: a physical examination with assessment of complaints and pain syndrome; measurement of oxyproline levels in blood and urine; and EQ-5D-3L surveys at 3, 6, 9, and 12 months.

Oxyproline was measured spectrophotometrically using acid hydrolysis followed by reaction with chloramine T; matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) was determined by sandwich ELISA (Cloud-Clone Corp., USA) with a detection wavelength of 450 nm; extracellular matrix (ECM) was assessed as total protein using the biuret method with spectrophotometric measurement at 550 nm; fibroblast mitotic activity (FMA) was evaluated morphologically on stained smears (Giemsa method) and calculated using the following formula:

$$MI = (\text{number of mitoses} / \text{total number of fibroblasts}) \times 100.$$

Research results and discussion. Comparison of treatment outcomes in patients with acute adhesive intestinal obstruction demonstrated the effectiveness of a comprehensive algorithm for predicting and preventing recurrence. The control group received standard therapy, while the main group was treated using individualized methods. Both groups were comparable in terms of age, sex, number of previous surgeries, and comorbidities, ensuring the reliability of the analysis.

Upon admission, all patients exhibited similar symptoms: pain, abdominal distension, nausea, vomiting, and delayed bowel transit (Fig. 2).

In the main group, the number of complaints per patient was higher, indicating a more severe course of the disease and thorough examination. Objectively, signs of dynamic obstruction were more frequently observed, including increased peristalsis, abdominal asymmetry, tympany, and abdominal wall tension (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Distribution pattern of main complaints in patients upon admission to the clinic

Figure 3. Distribution pattern of main complaints in patients upon admission to the clinic

In the control group, treatment was based on classical criteria: 48–72 hours of conservative therapy followed by a decision on surgery. During adhesiolysis, dense adhesions, mesenteric fusion, and intestinal ischemia were often observed, leading to organ trauma, resections, and complications, including multiple organ failure.

In the main group, the treatment strategy was determined in advance using laboratory markers and a prognostic model. This allowed for the identification of patients for early surgery with anti-adhesion prophylaxis, while avoiding unnecessary interventions. As a result, decision-making time was reduced and the frequency of intraoperative injuries decreased. Within a year, more than half of the patients in the control group required repeat surgeries, whereas in the main group, their number was reduced nearly by half. This was due not only to the use of barrier agents but also to more accurate risk stratification based on biomarkers—levels of oxyproline, MMP-9

activity, and fibroblast proliferation indicators.

Significant differences in the frequency of complications, repeat surgeries, and quality of life at 3, 6, and 12 months were already evident in the clinical analysis. This served as the basis for a more detailed study of laboratory and biochemical indicators, presented below. Extracellular matrix (ECM) indicators had already increased 1.6-fold above baseline by the 10th day after deserosalization, and more than doubled by 40–60 days, reflecting the accumulation of collagenous and non-collagenous components and active connective tissue synthesis. At high ECM levels, MMP-9 expression was elevated, consistently rising over time and performing a dual function—matrix degradation and regulation of cell proliferation.

The mitotic index of fibroblast activity (MIFA) proved to be most sensitive in the early period: on days 1–3, it exceeded the normal level fivefold, reaching its peak on day 10—a critical stage of fibrosis formation when prophylaxis is most effective. Correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between oxyproline and MMP-9 ($r = 0.86$; $p < 0.001$) and a negative correlation with MIFA ($r = -0.73$; $p < 0.01$), confirming the phased nature of the process and the possibility of laboratory monitoring of the transition from regeneration to fibrosis. An important practical finding was the established link between urinary oxyproline levels and the severity of adhesions, allowing its use as a non-invasive screening test. Clinically, patients with high levels more often exhibited severe forms requiring extensive surgery and were accompanied by recurrences within a year.

Figure 4. Postoperative complication dynamics according to the Clavien–Dindo classification criteria

Oxyproline, MMP-9, ECM, and MIFA demonstrated diagnostic and prognostic value. Based on these indicators, a risk stratification model was developed, also incorporating the acetylation phenotype. Patients were categorized by risk level (low, medium, high), which guided the management strategy: observation, barrier anti-adhesion agents, or early surgical intervention. Implementation of the model reduced the frequency of complications and repeat surgeries:

relaparotomies within a year decreased from 54.5% to 25.3%. In high-risk patients receiving anti-adhesion materials, oxyproline and MMP-9 levels decreased during the first 10–14 days postoperatively.

According to the Clavien–Dindo scale, grade III–IV complications in the main group decreased more than twofold (13.8% vs. 31.7%), with reductions in the incidence of multiple organ failure (4.5% vs. 14.3%) and mortality (2.7% vs. 7.9%). This confirms the effectiveness of individualized adhesion prevention (Figure 4).

Analysis of long-term outcomes using the EQ-5D-3L scale showed that patients in the main group exhibited more stable improvements in quality of life. At 3 months, good and satisfactory scores were observed in 66.3% of patients (compared to 48.2% in the control group). By 12 months, the proportion of patients with unsatisfactory outcomes did not exceed 21% (control group — 38%). Even patients with a severe medical history achieved sustained clinical and functional compensation when the algorithm was applied early (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Comparative dynamics of changes in patient scores according to the EQ-5D-3L questionnaire

The dynamics of rehospitalizations demonstrated the effectiveness of the comprehensive approach: recurrences requiring readmission occurred in 18.7% of patients in the main group and 41.5% in the control group. This reduces the burden on healthcare systems and improves quality of life.

Comparison of clinical and functional outcomes, complications, and recurrences confirms the high efficacy of the algorithm, which is also supported by economic analysis. Implementation of the algorithm nearly halves postoperative complications, recurrences, and repeat surgeries, minimizing the risk of severe multiple organ complications. The social impact is reflected in shorter rehabilitation periods, reduced disability, and faster return to work and self-care, particularly among working-age patients (over 40% of the cohort).

Conclusion

Acute adhesive intestinal obstruction (AAIO) is characterized by high clinical heterogeneity, with significant risks of recurrence, complications, and repeat surgeries. Traditional clinical signs (severe pain, dynamic obstruction, asymmetric distension, impaired bowel transit)

are insufficiently precise for predicting recurrence.

Experimental studies identified key biochemical markers of the adhesion process: oxyproline, MMP-9, extracellular matrix components, and the mitotic index of fibroblasts, whose dynamics correlate with stages of adhesion formation. Patients with high levels of oxyproline and MMP-9 had worse outcomes under standard management, supporting the rationale for early prophylactic intervention.

The use of a prognostic model based on clinical, biochemical, and morphometric data reduced grade III–V complications by 2.3 times, decreased relaparotomies to 25.3%, and improved quality of life. An individualized approach also reduces disability, accelerates outpatient adaptation, and shortens rehabilitation periods.

Thus, the proposed approach can be recommended for broad application in clinical practice, both in specialized surgical centers and in general healthcare facilities.

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